

Fekete-Szegö Problem for Subclasses of Analytic Functions Defined by New Integral Operator

Khalifa AlShaqsi

Abstract—The author introduced the integral operator, by using this operator a new subclasses of analytic functions are introduced. For these classes, several Fekete-Szegö type coefficient inequalities are obtained.

Keywords—Integral operator, Fekete-Szegö inequalities, Analytic functions.

I. INTRODUCTION AND DEFINITION

LET \mathcal{A} denote the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n, \quad (1)$$

which are analytic in the open unite disk $\mathbb{U} = \{z : z \in \mathbb{C} \text{ and } |z| < 1\}$.

Also let \mathcal{S} denote the subclasses of \mathcal{A} consisting of functions which are univalent in \mathbb{U} .

In [2] Fekete and Szegö proved a noticeable result that the estimate

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq 1 + 2 \exp\left(\frac{-2\mu}{1-\mu}\right)$$

holds for $f \in \mathcal{S}$ and for $0 \leq \mu \leq 1$. This inequality is sharp for each μ . The coefficient functional

$$\phi_\mu(f) = a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = \frac{1}{6} \left(f'''(0) - \frac{3\mu}{2} (f''(0))^2 \right)$$

on $f \in \mathcal{A}$ represents various geometric quantities as well as in the sense that this behaves well with respect to the rotation, namely

$$\phi_\mu(e^{-i\theta} f(e^{i\theta} z)) = e^{2i\theta} \phi_\mu(f), \quad (\theta \in \mathbb{R}).$$

In fact, other than the simplest case when

$$\phi_0(f) = a_3,$$

we have several important ones. For example,

$$\phi_1(f) = a_3 - a_2^2,$$

Nizwa College of Technology, Ministry of Manpower, Sultanate of Oman, Po.Box:75 P.C:612, (e-mail: khalifa.alshaqsi@nct.edu.om).

represent $S_f(0)/6$, where S_f denotes the Schwarzian derivative

$$S_f(z) = \left(\frac{f''(z)}{f'(z)} \right)' - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{f''(z)}{f'(z)} \right)^2.$$

Moreover, the first two non-trivial coefficients of the n -th root transform

$$(f(z^n))^{\frac{1}{n}} = z + c_{n+1} z^{n+1} + c_{2n+1} z^{2n+1} + \dots$$

of f with the power series (1), are written by

$$c_{n+1} = \frac{a_2}{n}$$

and

$$c_{2n+1} = \frac{a_3}{n} + \frac{(n-1)a_2^2}{2n^2}$$

so that

$$a_3 - \mu_2^2 = n(c_{2n+1} - \lambda c_{n+1}^2),$$

where

$$\lambda = \mu n + \frac{n-1}{2}$$

Thus, it is quite natural to ask about inequalities for ϕ_μ corresponding to subclasses of \mathcal{S} . This is called Fekete-Szegö problem. Actually many authors have considered this problem for typical classes of univalent functions.

Recently, in [1] the author introduced a certain integral operator $\mathcal{I} - c^\delta$ defined by :

$$\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z) = \frac{(1+c)^\delta}{\Gamma(\delta)} \int_0^1 t^{c-1} (\log 1/t)^{\delta-1} f(tz) dt, \quad (2)$$

where $c > 0$, $\delta > 1$ and $z \in \mathbb{U}$.

We also note that the operator $\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)$ defined by (1) can be expressed by the series expansion as following:

$$\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1+c}{k+c} \right)^\delta a_k z^k, \quad (3)$$

Obviously, we have, for $(\delta, \lambda \geq 0)$

$$\mathcal{I}_c^\delta (\mathcal{I}_c^\lambda f(z)) = \mathcal{I}_c^{\delta+\lambda} f(z). \quad (4)$$

and

$$\mathcal{I}_c^\delta (z f'(z)) = z (\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))'. \quad (5)$$

Moreover, from (3), it follows that

$$z(\mathcal{I}_c^{\delta+1} f(z))' = (c+1)\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z) - c\mathcal{I}_c^{\delta+1} f(z) \quad (6)$$

We note that :

- For $c = 0$ and $\delta = n$ (n is any integer), the multiplier transformation $\mathcal{I}_0^n f(z) = I^n f(z)$ was studied by Flett [3] and Salagean [4];
- For $c = 0$ and $\delta = -n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$), the differential operator $\mathcal{I}_0^{-n} f(z) = D^n f(z)$ was studied by Salagean [4];
- For $c = 1$ and $\delta = n$ (n is any integer), the operator $\mathcal{I}_1^n f(z) = \mathcal{I}^n f(z)$ was studied by Uralegaddi and Somanatha [5];
- For $c = 1$, the multiplier transformation $\mathcal{I}_1^\delta f(z) = \mathcal{I}^\delta f(z)$ was studied by Jung et al. [6];
- For $c = a - 1$ ($a > 0$), the integral operator $\mathcal{I}_{a-1}^\delta f(z) = \mathcal{I}_{a-1}^\delta f(z)$ was studied by Komatu [7];

Using the operator \mathcal{I}_c^δ , we now introduce the following classes:

Definition 1: we say that a function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is in the class $\mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$ if

$$\Re \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{b} \left(\frac{z(\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))'}{\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)} - 1 \right) \right\} > 0, \quad (c > 0, \delta \geq 0, b \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}, z \in \mathbb{U}). \quad (7)$$

Definition 2: we say that a function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is in the class $\mathcal{C}_{c,\delta}(b)$ if

$$\Re \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{b} \frac{z(\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))''}{\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)} \right\} > 0, \quad (c > 0, \delta \geq 0, b \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}, z \in \mathbb{U}). \quad (8)$$

Note that

$$f \in \mathcal{C}_{c,\delta}(b) \Leftrightarrow z f' \in \mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b). \quad (9)$$

In particular, we have starlike and convex function classes, $\mathcal{S}_{c,0}(1) = \mathcal{S}^*$ and $\mathcal{C}_{c,0}(1) = \mathcal{C}$, respectively.

We denote by P a class of the analytic functions in \mathbb{U} with

$$p(0) = 1 \text{ and } \Re\{p(z)\} > 0.$$

To prove our results, we need the following Lemmas considered by Duren [8] Ravichandran et al. [9].

Lemma 1: [8] Let $p \in P$ with $p(z) = 1 + c_1 z + c_2 z^2 + \dots$. Then

$$|c_n| \leq 2, \quad (n \geq 1).$$

Lemma 2: [9] Let $p \in P$ with $p(z) = 1 + c_1 z + c_2 z^2 + \dots$. Then for any complex number γ

$$|c_2 - \gamma c_1^2| \leq 2 \max\{1, |2\gamma - 1|\},$$

and the result is sharp for the functions given by

$$p(z) = \frac{1+z^2}{1-z^2}, \quad p(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}.$$

Lemma 3: [8] Let $p \in P$ with $p(z) = 1 + c_1 z + c_2 z^2 + \dots$. Then

$$\left| c_2 - \frac{1}{2} \lambda c_1^2 \right| \leq 2 + \frac{1}{2} (|\lambda - 1| - 1) |c_1|^2.$$

II. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 1: Let $c, \delta \geq 0; b \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. If $f \in \mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$, then

$$|a_2| \leq 2|b| \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^\delta,$$

$$|a_3| \leq |b| \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta \max\{1, |1+2b|\},$$

and

$$\left| a_3 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2} \right)^\delta a_2^2 \right| \leq |b| \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta.$$

Proof. Denote

$$\mathcal{I}_c^\delta = z + A_2 z^2 + A_3 z^3 + \dots$$

Then by (3), we can write

$$A_2 = \left(\frac{c+1}{c+2}\right)^\delta a_2, \quad A_3 = \left(\frac{c+1}{c+3}\right)^\delta a_3. \quad (10)$$

$$= \left| a_3 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2} \right)^\delta a_2 \right|$$

$$= \left| \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta (c_2 + bc_1^2) - \frac{b^2 c_1^2}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2} \right)^\delta \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^{2\delta} \right|$$

$$= \left| \frac{bc_2}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta \right|$$

$$\leq |b| \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta.$$

by the definition of the class $\mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$, there exists $p \in P$ such that:

$$1 + \frac{1}{b} \left(\frac{z(\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))'}{\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)} - 1 \right) = p(z),$$

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))'}{\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)} = 1 - b + bp(z),$$

so that

$$\frac{z(1 + 2A_2z + 3A_3z^2 + \dots)}{z + A_2z^2 + A_3z^3 + \dots} = 1 - b + b(1 + c_1z + c_2z^2 + \dots),$$

which implies the equality

$$z + 2A_2z^2 + 3A_3z^3 + \dots$$

$$= z + (A_2 + bc_1)z^2 + (A_3 + bc_1A_2 + bc_2)z^3 + \dots$$

Equating the coefficients of both side, we have

$$A_2 = bc_1, \quad A_3 = \frac{b}{2}(c_2 + bc_1^2), \quad (11)$$

so that, on account of (10)

$$a_2 = b \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^\delta c_1, \quad a_3 = \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta (c_2 + bc_1^2). \quad (12)$$

Taking into account (12) and Lemma 1, we obtain

$$|a_2| \leq 2|b| \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^\delta,$$

and Lemma 2

$$|a_3| = \left| \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta (c_2 + bc_1^2) \right|$$

$$\leq |b| \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta \max\{1, |1 + 2b|\}.$$

Moreover, by Lemma 1

as asserted.

Now, we consider functional $|a_3 - \mu a_2^2|$ for complex μ .

Theorem 2: Let $c, \delta \geq 0; b \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. If $f \in \mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$, then for $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$, we have

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq |b| \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta \max \left\{ 1, \left| 1 + 2b - 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)} \right)^\delta \right| \right\}.$$

Moreover for each μ , there is a function in $\mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$ such that equality holds.

Proof. Taking into account (12) we have

$$a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^\delta (c_2 + bc_1^2) - \mu b^2 c_1^2 \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^{2\delta}$$

$$= \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1} \right)^\delta (c_2 + \beta c_1^2), \quad (13)$$

where

$$\beta = -b + 2\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)} \right)^\delta.$$

Then, with the aid of Lemma 2, we obtain

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \quad (14)$$

$$\leq |b| \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1} \right)^\delta \max \left\{ 1, \left| 1 + 2b - 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)} \right)^\delta \right| \right\}.$$

as asserted. An examination of the proof shows that equality is attained for the first case when $c_1 = 0$ and $c_2 = 2$ and the corresponding $f \in \mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$ is given by

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))'}{\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)} = \frac{1 + (2b-1)z^2}{1-z^2}, \quad (15)$$

and likewise for the second case when $c_1 = c_2 = 2$ the corresponding $f \in \mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$ is given by

$$\frac{z(\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z))'}{\mathcal{I}_c^\delta f(z)} = \frac{1 + (2b-1)z}{1-z}, \quad (16)$$

respectively.

Taking $\delta = 0$ and $b = 1$ in Theorem 2, we have :

Corollary 1: [10] If $f \in \mathcal{S}^*$, then for $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$ we have

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \max\{1, |4\mu - 3|\}.$$

Moreover for each μ , there is a function in \mathcal{S}^* such that equality holds.

We next consider the case when μ and b are real. Then we have

Theorem 3: Let $c, \delta \geq 0; b > 0$. If $f \in \mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$, then for $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} b \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \left[1 + 2b - 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right] & \text{if } \mu \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta \\ b \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta & \text{if } \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta \leq \mu \leq \frac{1+b}{2b} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta \\ b \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \left[-1 - 2b + 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right] & \text{if } \mu \geq \frac{1+b}{2b} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta \end{cases}$$

Moreover for each μ , there is a function in $\mathcal{S}_{c,\delta}(b)$ such that equality holds.

Proof. By (14), we obtain

$$a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \left[c_2 - \frac{c_1^2}{2} + \frac{c_1^2}{2} \left(1 + 2b - 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right) \right]. \quad (17)$$

First, let $\mu \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta$. in this case, by (17), Lemma 1 and Lemma 3 give

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \left[2 - \frac{|c_1|^2}{2} + \frac{|c_1|^2}{2} \left(1 + 2b - 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right) \right] \leq b \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \left[1 + 2b - 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta \right].$$

Now let $\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta \leq \mu \leq \frac{1+b}{2b} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta$. Then, using the above calculations, we get

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq b \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta.$$

Finally, if $\mu \geq \frac{1+b}{2b} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta$, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |a_3 - \mu a_2^2| &\leq \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \\ &\left[2 - \frac{|c_1|^2}{2} + \frac{|c_1|^2}{2} \left(-1 - 2b + 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right) \right]^\delta \\ &\leq \frac{b}{2} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \\ &\left[2 + \frac{|c_1|^2}{2} \left(-2 - 2b + 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right) \right]^\delta \\ &\leq b \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \left[-1 - 2b + 4\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta\right]. \end{aligned}$$

Equality is attained for the second case on choosing $c_1 = 0, c_2 = 2$ in (15) and in (16) $c_1 = c_2 = 2; c_1 = 2i, c_2 = -2$ for the first and third case, respectively. Thus the proof is complete.

Using the relation (9), we easily obtain bounds of coefficients and a solution of the Fekete-Szegő problem in $\mathcal{C}_{c,\delta}$.

Theorem 4: Let $c, \delta \geq 0; b \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. If $f \in \mathcal{C}_{c,\delta}(b)$, then

$$|a_2| \leq |b| \left(\frac{c+2}{c+1}\right)^\delta,$$

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{|b|}{3} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \max\{1, |1 + 2b|\},$$

and

$$\left| a_3 - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{(c+1)(c+3)}{(c+2)^2}\right)^\delta a_2^2 \right| \leq \frac{|b|}{3} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta.$$

Reasoning in the same line as in proof of Theorem 2 obtain :

Theorem 5: Let $c, \delta \geq 0; b \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. If $f \in \mathcal{C}_{c,\delta}(b)$, then for $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$, we have

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|b|}{3} \left(\frac{c+3}{c+1}\right)^\delta \max \left\{ 1, \left| 1 + 2b - 3\mu b \left(\frac{(c+2)^2}{(c+1)(c+3)}\right)^\delta \right| \right\}.$$

Moreover for each μ , there is a function in $\mathcal{C}_{c,\delta}(b)$ such that equality holds.

By taking $\delta = 0$ and $b = 1$ in Theorem 5, we have

Corollary 2: [10] If $f \in \mathcal{C}^*$, then for $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$ we have

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \max\left\{\frac{1}{3}, |\mu - 1|\right\}.$$

Moreover for each μ , there is a function in \mathcal{C}^* such that equality holds.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Al-Shaqsi, *Strong differential subordinations obtained with new integral operator defined by polylogarithm function*, Int. J. Math. Math. Sci. **2014**, Article ID 260198, 6 pages, 2014.
- [2] M. Fekete and G. Szegő. *Eine bemerkung über ungerade schlichte funktionen* , 3J. Lond. Math. Soc. **8**, 85-89, 1993.
- [3] T. Flett, *The dual of an inequality of Hardy and Littlewood and some related inequalities*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **38**, 746-765, 1972.
- [4] G. Sălăgean, *Subclasses of univalent functions*, Lecture Note in Math.(Springer-Verlag), **1013**, 362-372, 1983.
- [5] B. Uralegaddi and C. Somanatha, *Certain classes of univalent functions*, In Current Topics in Analytic Function Theory, (Edited by H .M. Srivastava and S. Own), pp. 371-374, World Scientific, Singapore, 1992.
- [6] I. Jung, Y. Kim and H. Srivastava, *The Hardy space of analytic functions associated with certain one parameter families of integral operators*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **176**, 138-147, 1993.
- [7] Y. Komatu, *On analytic prolongation of a family of operator*, Math. (Cluj) **32** (55)(2), 141-145, 1990.
- [8] P. Duren. *Univalent functions* , Grundlehren der Mathematics. Wissenschaften, Bd., p259. Springer, New York 1983.
- [9] V. Ravichandran, A. Gangadharan and M. Darus. *Fekete-Szegő inequality for certain class of Bazilevic functions* , Far East J. Math. Sci. **15**, 171-180, 2004.
- [10] F. Keogh and E. Merkes. *A coefficient inequality for certain classes of analytic functions*, Proc. Amr. Math. Soc. **20**, 8-12, 1969.

Kalifa AlShaqsi received his Bachelor degree in Mathematics from Education College, Oman, in 1999 and MSc and PhD in Pure Mathematics (Complex Analysis) from National University of Malaysia in 2006 and 2009, respectively. Currently, he is a lecturer of Mathematics in Nizwa college of technology. He is also holding a post as Head of Mathematics Section. His special interest is in the geometric function theory and its applications.